

Chapter 26

Analysis in Social Media Applied to Business Intelligence and Analytics: A Literature Review

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Sentiment Analysis in Social Media Applied to Business Intelligence and Analytics: A Literature Review

Ana Sofia Cardoso^{1,*}, Beatriz Maia¹, Cristiana Maltez¹, Laura Batista¹, Fernanda Brito Correia¹

¹ Polytechnique University of Coimbra, Rua da Misericórdia, Lagar dos Cortiços, S. Martinho do Bispo, 3045-093, Coimbra, Portugal

*Corresponding author
a2021133158@isec.pt

Abstract

This paper is a literature review of Sentiment Analysis techniques applied to Social Media data. The review was guided by 4 Research Questions and analysed (1) the most effective Machine Learning algorithms, (2) common evaluation metrics used to assess performance, (3) contributions to Business Intelligence and Analytics, and (4) main limitations. Following Kitchenham's methodology and PRISMA framework, were analysed 14 recent studies, published between 2021 and 2024 and obtained from IEEE Xplore. The analysis revealed that these studies employed diverse Machine Learning models, ranging from traditional supervised and unsupervised approaches to advanced Deep Learning methods. The studies demonstrated that Deep Learning models, particularly LSTM and Bi-LSTM, outperformed traditional approaches, achieving accuracy rates up to 99.4%, with performance evaluated using several metrics. Furthermore, the literature analysis showed that Sentiment Analysis significantly contributed to the field of Business Intelligence and Analytics by enabling real-time customer insights, by supporting data-driven decisions, and by identifying market trends. However, the analysed studies highlighted persistent challenges in detection of sarcasm, multilingual content processing, informal language handling, and computational demands when using Deep Learning models. This literature review can guide the investigation of Sentiment Analysis in Social Media, while identifying future research directions.

Keywords: Sentiment Analysis, Social Media Data, Business Intelligence and Analytics, Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Literature Review

1 Introduction

Sentiment Analysis (SA) has emerged as a powerful technique for understanding public opinion and emotional responses expressed through online platforms. At its core, SA evaluates whether the tone of a given text is positive, negative, or neutral by employing algorithms that assess the context and emotional weight of words. This analytical approach offers diverse applications, especially in Business Intelligence and Analytics (BI&A), where companies leverage sentiment insights to understand consumer behaviour, improve customer experience, and refine marketing strategies [1]. Moreover, Social Media (SM) platforms generate vast amounts of user-generated content daily, making them valuable sources for tracking trends, detecting emerging issues, and assessing brand reputation.

Recent advancements in traditional Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) have improved the performance of SA systems [2], with research evolving from traditional ML approaches to sophisticated Neural Networks architectures [3]. However, challenges remain, including sarcasm detection, informal and multilingual language handling, and high computational costs of DL approaches [4]. SM platforms, like Twitter present additional complexities due to data noise, such as slang, emojis, and hashtags, posing challenges for accurate sentiment classification [5]. Despite these advances, current literature lacks comprehensive comparative analysis of ML techniques specifically applied to SM SA, within BI&A contexts. Many studies have concentrated on specific techniques without systematically evaluating various approaches, which has hindered the comprehensive understanding of the best methodologies for real-world applications. This literature review seeks to fill this gap by examining SA techniques applied to SM data, with the goal of enhancing the understanding of current ML approaches, their effectiveness, limitations, and potential future developments.

Four Research Questions (RQ) guided the analysis and are presented in Table 1. In this table RQ_N is the

number of the RQ and in the third column is given the RQ motivation.

This paper is structured as follows, in section 2 is presented the methodology used in this literature review, in section 3 is included the analysis and discussion done, in section 4 the conclusions are presented and directions for future research are proposed. The final section lists the references used along the paper.

Table 1. List of the RQs

RQ_N	RQ	Motivation
RQ1	What are the most effective ML techniques used?	To identify and compare ML algorithms currently employed for SA on SM platforms that deliver optimal performance
RQ2	What evaluation metrics are commonly used to assess the performance?	How researchers measure and compare the effectiveness of different SA approaches
RQ3	How did SA approaches contribute to the field of BI&A?	How SA insights from SM translate to actionable BI&A to support strategic decisions
RQ4	What are the main limitations?	To address the limitations and challenges of current techniques to highlight opportunities for future research and improvement

2 Methodology

This section outlines the approach adopted for conducting this literature review. It was followed the Kitchenham's methodology [6], supplemented by the PRISMA framework diagram [7] to ensure transparency and reproducibility.

The planning phase defined the search strategy and selection criteria. Considering the RQs, the following search string was defined: "sentiment analysis" AND ("business intelligence" OR "business analytics" OR "data analytics") AND "machine learning" AND "social media". This search was executed exclusively in the IEEE Xplore digital library, which houses high-quality publications in computer science and engineering fields. To ensure contemporary findings, we applied several preconditions to our search, namely the publication years 2021 onwards and the language English.

To ensure the relevance and methodological rigor of the selected studies, we defined specific inclusion criteria (IC) and exclusion criteria (EC) that guided our selection process, listed in Table 2, where IC_N is the number of each IC and EC_N is the number of each EC.

Table 2 - Inclusion and exclusion criteria

IC_N	IC	EC_N	EC
IC1	Studies that applied ML	EC1	Studies without experimental validation
IC2	Studies with experimental results and performance metrics	EC2	Studies where the title, or focus, was not on SA using ML applied to SM
IC3	Titles that included SA and ML	EC3	Studies that focused on a specific country or region
		EC4	Studies that focused on pandemic or public health crises (e.g., COVID-19)

These criteria allowed filtering the initial search results and focusing on studies that provided empirical evidence of ML applications for SA in general SM contexts, excluding narrowly focused or non-experimental works that would not substantially contribute to addressing our RQs. The number of articles selected each year from 2021 to 2024 based on the IC increased from 1 in 2021 to 4 in 2022, remained stable with 4 in 2023, and increased slightly to 5 in 2024. Till March 2025 weren't found any papers based on the specified criteria.

The literature review protocol implemented is described with the PRISMA flow diagram (Figure 1). Initially, the search in the IEEE Xplore database identified 121 records for screening. The screening process was conducted in 2 sequential phases. At first, the titles of all 121 papers were examined, which led to the exclusion of 84 papers. In the second phase, the abstracts of the remaining 37 papers were analysed, which resulted in the exclusion of an additional 23 papers. After applying our IC and EC during the screening phase, 107 records were excluded. The remaining 14 studies were sought for retrieval, all of which were successfully accessed and included in the final review.

Figure 1 - PRISMA flow diagram of the articles search and selection

3 Analysis and Discussion

This section synthesizes the key findings from the literature review while addressing the defined RQs. By systematically analysing 14 selected studies on SA in SM, this review provides a comprehensive exploration of ML techniques, their applications, and inherent challenges. Additionally, it examines the lexicon-based approach, a widely used SA method that relies on predefined sentiment dictionaries to classify text as positive, negative, or neutral. This method, often used independently or in hybrid models, is significant in SA due to its interpretability and efficiency in processing large volumes of text.

A. Studies Goals

The selected studies explored SA in various contexts using diverse techniques. Their main objectives, summarized in Error: Reference source not found, were to understand and classify emotions and opinions in textual data to gain valuable insights for different applications.

Table 3 – Studies goals

Goals	Reference
Develop a decision support framework for customers using Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis (ABSA) and Fuzzy Analytic Hierarchy Process	[1]
Build a robust model for SA in tweets and Facebook posts based on a hybrid Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN)- Gated Recurrent Units (GRU) approach	[2]
Investigate signs of emotional distress in online spaces through ML algorithms	[3]

Goals	Reference
Identify the main challenges of SA to help new researchers define research problems	[4]
Practical application and comparative analysis of the effectiveness of ML algorithms for SA	[5]
Understand SA systems that ignore or normalize elongated words and propose a new lexicon-based SA system that considers elongated words to calculate the sentiment level	[8]
Analyse sentiment in Twitter data using different ML models and lexicon-based approaches, comparing their results	[9]
Present a technique for analysing trends on Twitter, predicting emotions in tweets	[10]
Discover food-related sentiments among SM users and analysing attitudes based on food reviews	[11]
Develop a bio-inspired classification algorithm to classify sentiments in big data. Specifically, propose a Robust Optimization (RO) to identify the most valuable features for SA	[12]
Perform a unified SA of multiple comments on SM and improve the accuracy of SA by modifying the information gain method and applying it to Naive Bayes (NB) and Bi-LSTM models	[13]
Analyse SM data and extract valuable insights using advanced analytics techniques, applying clustering algorithms	[14]
Analyse user comments on Reddit, detect recurring patterns, extract relevant insights and perform a comparative analysis between CPU-based and GPU-accelerated AI processing for SA	[15]
Use a large dataset of tweets and advanced ML techniques to analyse ChatGPT public sentiment	[16]

They addressed challenges in SA, developed and evaluated models for specific data characteristics, and examined sentiments around tools like ChatGPT, opinions on food or electronic products, and signs of emotional distress. Some studies also focused on optimizing processes using clustering, GPU parallel processing, or combining ML algorithms with lexicon-based approaches. Overall, the common goal was to enhance the accuracy and effectiveness of SA to better understand the emotional landscape in textual data from various sources.

B. Machine Learning Techniques Applied to Sentiment Analysis

This section addresses RQ1, which analyse the most effective ML techniques for SA on SM identified by researchers. Various ML algorithms applied to SA on SM were identified in the 14 selected studies. Table 4 to Table 6 provide a detailed overview of the identified techniques, categorized by their approach types, highlighting the strengths and weaknesses noted by the studies. Supervised machine learning models, which are trained on labelled datasets, learn the relationships between input features and sentiment outputs, allowing for sentiment classification predictions from annotated Social Media text data.

The most prevalent supervised techniques in SA included Tree-based algorithms, namely Random Forest (RF), used in 1 study and Decision Trees (DT), used in 3 studies. RF's ensemble approach mitigates overfitting, while effectively handling high-dimensional and noisy SM data. On the other hand, DT, while simpler, offers interpretability advantages for understanding feature importance in sentiment expression. Logistic Regression (LR) and NB were used in four and five studies respectively, remaining effective baseline models. NB is computationally light but assumes feature independence, while LR offers a good balance of speed and performance for real-time tasks, K-Nearest Neighbour (KNN), used in three studies, classifies based on similarity to nearby data points but is mainly used for classification. Support Vector Machine (SVM) featured in five studies, find optimal hyperplanes to separate classes, showing high accuracy in both binary and multiclass sentiment tasks. LinearSVC, used in one study, is a linear SVM variant effective in high-dimensional text classification.

Unsupervised methods were less common, used mainly when labelled data was scarce, allowing pattern detection in SM data without pre-labelled sentiment annotations. K-Means, cited in one study, clusters data into k predefined clusters by iteratively assigning points to the nearest centroid, minimizing squared distances between points and cluster centroids. DBSCAN, mentioned in one study, finds dense clusters

separated by sparse areas, but struggles with noise handling.

Deep Learning approaches were frequently employed in SM analysis due to their capability to capture complex linguistic patterns and contextual information. CNN were mentioned in three studies. Although CNN are traditionally associated with image processing, they have been successfully adapted for Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks, including SA. In this context, CNN identify local patterns, such as phrases or n-grams, by treating text as a one-dimensional signal. They apply convolutional filters to input sequences to learn features that represent important linguistic patterns and specific word combinations. Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) were highlighted in one study for their ability to process sequential data by maintaining hidden states that capture information about previous words. This makes them valuable for tasks where word order and context are crucial. However, RNNs face limitations with long sequences due to the vanishing gradient problem. Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTMs), mentioned in three studies, address this issue with memory cells that maintain information over long sequences, capturing context and dependencies. Bidirectional LSTMs (Bi-LSTMs), noted in two studies, enhance this by processing sequences in both directions, capturing context from both past and future words. BERT, mentioned in one study, is a revolutionary language model in NLP that understands bidirectional word context within sentences, enabling more accurate interpretations through attention mechanisms.

Table 4 - Supervised models used in the analysed papers

Algorithm	Strengths	Weaknesses
DT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy to interpret and visualize and useful as a simple baseline for comparison [16] • Very easy to understand and interpret [3] • [5] did not present any strength 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prone to overfitting, especially with noisy data and lower performance compared to more advanced models [16] • Lower performance with noisy data [3] • [3] and [5] did not present any weaknesses
KNN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An intuitive and simple approach [14] • [3], [15] did not present strengths 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Generally, it is primarily used for classification [14] • [3], [15] did not present weaknesses
LinearSVC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achieved an accuracy exceeding 80% [11] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • [11] did not present weaknesses
LR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Commonly used for data classification [3] • Provides probabilistic predictions, making it useful for classification tasks [5] • [11] and [15] did not present strengths 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can struggle with more intricate tasks or datasets with a high dimensionality of features and assumes a linear relationship between independent and dependent variables [5] • [11] and [15] did not present weaknesses
NB	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More efficient and accurate than SVM when applied to training sets with a large number of evaluations [11] • Performs well on large text datasets and high accuracy in some studies [3] • [5], [9], [13] did not present strengths 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assumes feature independence, not always true [3] • Performance is generally lower than more modern models like LSTM [3], [11] • [5], [9], [13] did not present any weaknesses
RF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combined multiple DT, improving robustness and accuracy of predictions, reducing the risk of overfitting and able to handle missing data efficiently [15] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Training multiple DT can be time-consuming and require significant computational resources and due to its ensemble nature, it is harder to interpret and understand individual DTs compared to a single DT [15]

Algorithm	Strengths	Weaknesses
SVM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maximizes the margin between classes, which helps improve generalization and classification accuracy [9] • Effective in high-dimensional spaces, good generalization even with limited data, high performance with high-dimensional data like text and works well even with small, labelled datasets [3] • [5], [15] and [16] did not present strengths. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May not perform well with non-linear data [9] • It can have high computational costs on CPUs due to the temporal complexity that grows quadratically with the number of samples [15] • Slow training on large datasets, more complex in terms of result interpretation and difficult to tune, especially for multi-class problems [16] • High computational cost with large datasets [3] • [5] did not present weaknesses

Table 5 - Unsupervised models used in the analysed papers

Algorithm	Strengths	Weaknesses
DBSCAN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • allows to discover clusters of arbitrary shapes, unlike algorithms like K-Means that tend to find more spherical clusters [14] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not suitable for noise cluster analysis [14]
K-means	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Easy-to-use technique, it scales to large datasets, ensures convergence, is simple to implement and adapt easily to new examples, covering clusters of various sizes and shapes [14] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • K-means may be inaccurate when the data includes noise or irregularly shaped clusters [14]

Table 6 - Deep Learning models used in the analysed papers

Algorithm	Strengths	Weaknesses
BERT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have made substantial strides in recent years in NLP applications involving SA and provided the highest level of accuracy when analysing sentiment in airline review data [1] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • May have limitations in sentiment scoring scale and in identifying mixed sentiments [1]
Bi-LSTM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Captured two-way semantic dependencies or context, improving accuracy in SA [9], [13] • Ability to learn complex patterns in data [13] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Computationally expensive and required more resources compared to simpler models, making them slower to train and deploy [9], [13]
CNN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable for short text in SA and efficient in parallel computation [2] • Outperformed LT, showing higher classification accuracy [10] • Effectively extract spatial and short-term dynamic features [3] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cannot model context beyond local features and struggled with long-term dependencies in sequences [2] • [3] and [10] did not present weaknesses
LSTM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excellent performance on sequential data, such as text [9], [16] • Very effective for Sain NLP, excellent for sequential data like tweets and messages, and outperforms classical models in many studies [3] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High computational cost and longer training time and needs large volumes of labelled data to train effectively [16] • Required high computational resources and longer training time compared to traditional models [3] • Lacks bidirectional context [9]

Algorithm	Strengths	Weaknesses
RNN	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Extensively used in text analysis, have shown great potential for SA and due to their complex structure and the ability to understand context, DL models like RNN, performed well [9] 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> [9] did not present weaknesses

C. Evaluation Metrics

This section addresses RQ2, which examines the evaluation metrics commonly used to assess the performance of SA techniques on SM. The selection of appropriate metrics was crucial for accurately measuring and comparing the effectiveness of different algorithms and approaches. The analysis of the 14 selected studies revealed a consistent set of main metrics employed across SA research (Table 7).

Table 7 - Metrics used in the analysed papers

Metric	Reference
Accuracy	[2], [3], [5], [10], [12], [13], [15]
AUC	[3]
Confusion Matrix	[2], [3], [15]
F1-Score	[2], [3], [5], [8], [11], [13], [15], [16]
Precision	[2], [3], [5], [8], [11], [13], [15], [16]
Recall	[2], [3], [15]
ROC Curve	[2], [3]
Sentiment Score (BERT)	[1]
Specificity	[15]

D. Datasets Used

SA on SM using ML relied on various datasets to train and evaluate models. Twitter represented the most widely explored source, with popular datasets including Sentiment140 [9], tweet collections of 31,962 samples [10], 236,275 ChatGPT-related tweets [16], and millions of tweets for SA [3], as well as informal chats shared on the platform alongside Facebook and personal messaging [8]. Beyond Twitter, other studies analysed sentiment on Facebook, using data from posts and interactions [15], often combined with Twitter data through official APIs [2], [14]. E-commerce platforms constituted another major data source, particularly Amazon datasets including Fine Food Reviews [11] and product-specific collections (BOO, CPA, MTV, HAK) [12], plus customer feedback from Amazon, eBay, Flipkart, and Ajio [1]. Additional sources included Reddit subreddit data via PRAW API [15], Weibo comments (10,000 samples) [13], and established benchmark datasets such as Stanford Sentiment Treebank, IMDB, and Amazon Reviews [4]. Additionally, some studies incorporated multimodal approaches, combining text with audio, images, and video for psychological analysis [3]. Data collection methods included API access and web scraping for WhatsApp, Twitter, and Facebook data [14], and a CSV format, already processed to remove explicit emotions, containing six fields [5]. This dataset diversity enabled ML models to capture varied linguistic patterns, cultural contexts, and sentiment expressions across different SM platforms and domains.

E. Results Obtained

Addressing RQ1, the analysis of the 14 studies revealed clear patterns regarding which ML approaches delivered the best performance in SA of SM data. Several studies highlighted the superiority of LSTM and Bi-LSTM models, especially for sequential data such as tweets and reviews [13]. Bi-LSTM model often performed the best, due to its ability to capture bidirectional semantic dependencies. A study on ChatGPT

[16] concluded that the LSTM model demonstrated superior performance across all evaluation metrics. CNNs were effective at extracting local patterns in text and have achieved high accuracy, such as in a study on identifying hashtags in tweets [10], where CNN outperformed LR with an accuracy of approximately 95%. The combination of CNNs for local feature extraction and GRUs for sequential modelling has demonstrated superior results compared to individual models and traditional ML methods in SA of tweets and Facebook posts. One study reported an accuracy of 89.5% for a hybrid CNN-GRU model [2]. BERT pre-trained language model demonstrated significant progress, achieving the highest accuracy in SA on airline review data in one study. BERT was also used to obtain sentiment scores for features in ABSA [1]. Furthermore, a study that compared SVM and NB using movie reviews concluded that NB was more effective [11]. In a study that used the K-Means clustering algorithm to analyse SM data [14], the results showed the effectiveness of K-Means in grouping similar data and detecting trends in conversations from collected data. Another study found that Maximum Entropy performed best in classifying tweets related to McDonald's and KFC, when compared to other supervised algorithms such as NB, SVM, DT and Bagging. In contrast, in an analysis of tweets about attacks, a word frequency model combined with DT, LinearSVC, LR and NB algorithm achieved an accuracy of 83% [3]. In a study that analysed Reddit data, RF achieved the highest accuracy rate of 99.4%, followed by SVM and KNN, while LR had the lowest accuracy. RO, a bio-inspired classifier proposed in [12], achieved higher accuracy and F1-measure compared to other techniques in SA big data. Another study compared NB and SVM with RNN, LSTM and Bi-LSTM for SA of tweets, concluding that DL models generally delivered more accurate results, with Bi-LSTM achieving the best accuracy of 81.33% and F1-score of 81.54% [9]. In the study [8], a new lexicon-based system that considered long words outperformed traditional systems that ignored them, achieving F1-score rates of 81% to 96% on datasets of informal Facebook conversations, Tweets, and personal chats. The average F1-score increase was 21.22% when including long words. The results indicated that the ML approach outperformed DL and lexicon-based methods, in terms of accuracy, in other studies, mentioned in [5]. In [4], no experimental tests were carried out directly, only results from other studies were referenced.

In summary, DL techniques, particularly LSTM, Bi-LSTM, CNN and hybrid models such as CNN-GRU, together with transformers such as BERT, consistently demonstrated high effectiveness in SA across a variety of domains. However, traditional ML methods such as SVM, NB and RF remain relevant and can be quite effective depending on the dataset and context. The choice of the most appropriate technique depends on the specific characteristics of the data, the objectives of the analysis, and the available computational resources.

F. Contributions to Business Intelligence and Analytics

This section addresses RQ3, which considers how SA approaches contribute to the field of BI&A, particularly in strategic decision-making, by analysing the selected studies. It was observed the following contributions, the deep understanding of customer opinions and feedback about products, services, brands, and even competitors, the support to strategic decision-making in business and marketing, identifying market trends and predicting consumer behaviour and the detection of implicit opinions and nuances in language. By analysing comments on e-commerce platforms, SM and other online sources, companies can identify what customers appreciate and what aspects need improvement. For example, the study [11] analysed Amazon food reviews revealing that most sentiments were positive but also revealed negative sentiments that can guide food companies to improve their products. Similarly, SA of restaurant reviews on TripAdvisor helped to understand customer satisfaction with aspects such as food, ambiance, and service. ABSA, discussed in [1], provided an even more granular understanding, identifying the sentiments expressed toward specific features of a product or service. For example, when analysing airline reviews, ABSA could identify positive sentiments about food, but negative sentiments about flights, providing actionable insights for improvements. Also, SA provided crucial insights that supported strategic decision-making in business and marketing. Understanding public sentiment towards their products and services, as well as those of their competitors, enables companies to adjust their marketing, communication, and product development strategies more effectively. The article [4] mentioned the ability to derive market intelligence from microblogs such as Twitter through SA, which could inform decisions about marketing campaigns and

new product launches. Analysing tweets about electronic products could shed light on public perception and help inform strategic decisions related to those products [4]. Study [12] highlighted how SA became an essential business tool, providing valuable insights into consumer thoughts, helping to define better marketing strategies and informing product development decisions. SA enables businesses to identify emerging market trends and predict consumer behaviour. By monitoring public sentiment around specific events, products or topics, organizations can anticipate changes in consumer preferences and adapt their strategies accordingly. The study [8] used Twitter data to detect public sentiment and predict future stock market movements, demonstrating the potential of SA in predicting trends and understanding market reactions to events. Real-time SA of SM conversations can help identify emerging trends [14]. SA of film reviews, for example, can help predict their commercial success, influencing production and distribution decisions [13]. Advanced SA approaches could detect implicit opinions and nuances in language, such as sarcasm, irony, negation, and the use of elongated words to express intense emotion. Study [8] proposed a system that considers elongated words like "happyyyyyy" to calculate the level of sentiment, arguing that these words intensify the expressed emotion. Ignoring these nuances, as traditional systems do, can lead to an underestimation of the customer's true sentiment. Detecting and handling negation is crucial to avoid incorrect sentiment classifications. For example, the sentence "dislike" expresses a negative sentiment, even though it contains the word "like" which, on its own, would be positive [12].

The 14 studies analysed in this review demonstrated how SA on SM can anticipate changes in consumer behaviour, allowing companies to respond more quickly to market preferences. These insights support data-driven decision-making, enabling organizations to adjust their marketing strategies, improve customer service, and guide product development. When integrated into BI&A platforms, SA enriches traditional analytics with emotional and behavioural dimensions, offering a more comprehensive view of customer perception.

G. Limitations and Challenges

This section addresses RQ4, highlighting the limitations and challenges identified by the selected papers. These obstacles hindered the accuracy and reliability of SA across various domains. A major challenge is the reliance on correct spelling, as many SA models struggle with misspelled words or informal language common in social media and online discussions. Although some advanced techniques attempt to correct spelling errors, they are not always accurate, leading to potential misclassifications. Table 8 provides a detailed overview of these limitations and the corresponding studies. Despite these challenges, ongoing advancements in NLP and ML offer promising solutions. Addressing these issues will lead to more robust SA models, enhancing decision-making and providing more accurate insights into consumer sentiment across digital platforms.

Table 8 - Limitations identified used in the analysed papers

Limitations	Reference
Complexity in implementing context-aware sentiment models. Lack of high-quality labelled benchmark datasets	[1]
High computational demands of hybrid models (e.g., CNN-GRU)	[2]
Difficulty handling spelling errors and informal language. Lack of contextual understanding in SM posts	[2], [3], [8]
Difficulty detecting sarcasm, irony, and denial	[4], [11]
Evaluation limited to training and test sets only, risking overfitting	[5]
High computational complexity and long training times of DL models. Need for large, labelled datasets and limited annotation quality	[9]
Dependency on specific platforms like Twitter and e-commerce platforms	[10], [12]
Layer depth constraints in models like Bi-LSTM limiting their ability to capture complex linguistic patterns	[13]

Limitations	Reference
Limitations of K-Means: sensitive to noise, outliers, and only identifies spherical clusters.	[14]
Challenges in data collection: restricted tools and APIs, unrepresentative filtering methods	
The article does not explicitly detail the limitations found during the execution of this specific study.	[15]
Restriction to specific languages, such as English-only datasets	[16]

4 Conclusions

This literature review was motivated by the increasing complexity and volume of sentiment-rich data generated on SM, necessitating more effective ML techniques for analysis. To address this, a literature review was conducted, analysing 14 studies from IEEE Xplore published between 2021 and 2024. The review addressed the following research questions: (RQ1) DL techniques, particularly LSTM, Bi-LSTM, and hybrid models such as CNN-GRU, were identified as the most effective for SA on SM; (RQ2) Accuracy, F1-score, and Precision emerged as the most commonly used evaluation metrics, underscoring the need for multifaceted performance assessments; (RQ3) SA significantly contributed to BI&A by providing deep insights into customer opinions, supporting strategic decision-making, identifying market trends, and detecting linguistic nuances; (RQ4) key limitations included difficulties in processing complex language, high computational demands, domain and platform dependencies, and challenges in detecting linguistic nuances such as sarcasm and irony. This literature review advances the state of the art by elucidating current best practices in sentiment classification and highlighting the limitations that impede broader adoption. These findings can inform the refinement of future SA models and applications. Future research should focus on developing multilingual and low-resource sentiment models, enhancing mechanisms for detecting sarcasm and irony, and creating more efficient model architectures suitable for real-time analysis. Interdisciplinary efforts that integrate NLP with sociolinguistics and cultural studies may further enhance the interpretability and applicability of sentiment insights.

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